

Interview with Music Composer Kenji Kawai

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CoolJapan.es

On the occasion of his attendance at the first edition of the MOSMA —Movie Score Málaga— film music festival, which welcomed experts from all over the world, we had the opportunity to meet the composer Kenji Kawai in person, who very kindly granted us an interview. The Japanese musician treated the attendees to a session in which he explained a little about how he works and how he aligns visual material from cinema and animation with his music, even with his laptop in hand.

In addition, Kawai was awarded the MOSMA Distant Worlds prize during the event, presented by the organisers in recognition of his long and distinguished career as a musician. During the festival's closing concert, he himself performed alongside the Málaga City Symphony Orchestra and the Ziryab Choir from Córdoba at the Cervantes Theatre.

Kenji Kawai with his award, the MOSMA Distant Worlds, at the exit of the festival's closing concert, in which he took part and during which we were able to listen to a selection of tracks composed by him

Born in the special ward of Shinagawa, Tokyo —sharing his birthplace with personalities such as filmmaker Akira Kurosawa and the current Empress of Japan, Michiko— and still residing there today, Kenji Kawai is a self-made composer. He began his musical studies at the Shobi Academy after spending some time studying Nuclear Engineering; however, he did not stick with music studies for long, as he was a very restless individual: he was not attracted to classes and preferred going out, having fun, and diving directly into work. Alongside some colleagues, he formed his own fusion rock band called Muse —not to be confused with the other band of the same name—. The band gained significant experience, though they eventually split, each pursuing a solo career. Kawai developed a very personal sense of music, incorporating both Western elements from various musical genres and traditional Japanese music.

The artist chose to dedicate himself entirely to musical composition, with his first works being the soundtracks for adaptations of Rumiko Takahashi's mangas —Maison Ikkoku and Ranma ½—. He also worked on the series Devilman, by the renowned Gō Nagai. While closely associated with anime series, he also ventured into film, collaborating on projects by the famous director Mamoru Oshii —who directed, among others, the adaptations of Patlabor and the live-action film Avalon, praised both for the film itself and for its outstanding original soundtrack composed by Kawai.

It was through his work on Oshii's films that Kawai achieved international fame, thanks to his immortal contribution to what many, including myself, consider the greatest Japanese animated film of all time: Ghost in the Shell (1995), based on Masamune Shirow's manga of the same name. He would return to contribute to its sequel, Innocence (2004), also highly acclaimed.

Kawai has also shared his talent with the world of video games and J-Horror —a topic that Kawai himself would discuss during the interview. From then until the present day, he has continued to work on Japanese animation and film, including the Death Note movies, the anime Gundam 00, Yat Anshin!, the film The Sky Crawlers —also by Oshii—, the animated series Fate/Stay Night, and many more.

Interview with Kenji Kawai

Cool Japan: First of all, thank you for your time, Mr Kawai. It's a pleasure. To start, how long have you been interested in working as a composer? Did you ever consider being a performer or musician as well? Did you want from the beginning to link your professional career to the world of music? We understand you even studied engineering.

Kenji Kawai: As a child, I wanted to be more of an engineer than a musician. Perhaps when I was around twenty years old, I started becoming interested in composing music. More than interest... my career has been a bit casual. It wasn't something I decided in a definitive way; it gradually emerged. It was less a conscious decision than a natural progression, as my interest kept growing. That's how it all began.

I have never formally studied composition, nor followed a conservatory path. I didn't follow the typical trajectory of a composer. My life and career haven't followed the standard route of "learned composition, then wrote music, then worked in it..." It rather developed naturally. My interest in pursuing this work grew steadily within me.

At first, I was an amateur guitarist. I saw a poster for a band competition. If we won... we would earn money and a car. I thought I would enter and give it my all. We won the money and the car. After this, record labels offered our band —Muse— a chance to debut; it was an instrumental band, without vocals, in the fusion genre, but it wasn't very popular, as it wasn't a trendy style. We had formed it for the competition. It was an instant decision, so we didn't think of it as having much future.

I enjoyed studio musician work; we simply arrived at the studio, opened the score, and recorded. My problem was that I never read the scores properly due to vision issues. I thought then... since I couldn't read well and I loved music, why not write it myself?

Kawai with his laptop, explaining to the attendees of his lecture part of the composition process he follows when working on an anime. Later, he connected it to the audio system of the Cervantes Theatre so that the audience could listen to the different audio layers he usually adds to a composition.

Cool Japan: Your career is closely associated with director Mamoru Oshii in the eyes of fans. Could you tell us what it's like for you to work with him? How did you start collaborating?

Kenji Kawai: Well, after what I've already told you, one day I was composing music for a musical in my studio when a director came by to listen to it. He then asked me if I would compose music for his works, his films. That director's name is Mamoru Oshii.

I started working for him, and then the offers started pouring in—more and more assignments. As his films became famous in the West, I also began receiving more and more opportunities from outside Japan.

Mamoru is the person who has influenced me the most during a collaboration. He trusts me completely and lets me work freely, in my own way... but he does give hints. For example, in *Ghost in the Shell*: for the first film, Oshii asked me to include drums, including taiko, the traditional Japanese drum. There are sequences in which the drums appear as the main focus, and then other sounds and elements are gradually added. For me, it's very rewarding to start from just a single instrument.

Most directors ask for things like “make it happier” or “make it sadder”... but Mamoru is the only one who asks for specific instruments or elements. For me, that's very important.

Cool Japan: Speaking of your work with renowned Japanese directors, could you also talk about your experience composing for the films of Hideo Nakata, usually associated with the Japanese horror genre?

Kenji Kawai: I met him through the project *The Ring*. I was involved in composing the music for the film and also worked closely with the sound team and Nakata himself on certain sequences.

At first, he seemed a little intimidating; he inspired fear and respect, but in reality he's very playful. He's nothing like what you'd expect from someone directing that kind of film. He's always joking, telling jokes—but they're not always funny [laughs]. I'm afraid that if you don't react to his jokes, he gets upset [laughs]. He's a kind person, very good-natured, and his professionalism and pursuit of perfection are truly admirable.

Cool Japan: What is your favourite musical genre? Do you have, for example, a particular fondness for film music? Besides composing it, do you like listening to it? What are your main influences, both musical and literary?

Kenji Kawai: I like... everything! I'm passionate about cheerful music. I like classical composers such as Elgar. And I really enjoy, speaking of cheerful music, the work of Burt Bacharach. He has influenced me a lot. I also like many other artists from different genres, like The Carpenters, Carole King, Santana... and I really like Deep Purple. The fusion rock genre influenced me a lot as well—when I was in Muse, we played fusion. At that time (when I was starting), there were many musicians of all genres, all very good.

As for film music... my father used to play a lot of film music at home when I was small. That probably influenced me a bit [laughs]. He played, for example, the music from *Moulin Rouge*—the 1952 version.

Kenji Kawai with his interpreter Kayoko Morimoto, who is also a professional musician

Cool Japan: Could you tell us a bit about the process you follow when composing your works? What motivates you? For example, do you listen to other music while writing your own?

Kenji Kawai: The image—the visual I’m going to work with. A visual reference. When I see the image, for example from an animation film I’ll be working on, ideas start coming to me. Both the sounds and the type of music that the piece will need begin to take shape, what would fit it.

I also always take into account the director’s requests or hints. If I don’t have at least an image, an idea, or some suggestion from the director, I can’t compose anything for that project; I get blocked. I really can’t believe there are people who say that just by doing simple tasks like taking a walk, music suddenly comes to them. That doesn’t happen to me!

Cool Japan: Following up on that... when working on an animation series or film, how involved are you in the project? For example, there are sequences where the music is fully integrated with the scene, like the dollhouse scene in *Ghost in the Shell: Innocence*.

Kenji Kawai: I can’t compose for them without working closely together. I think this is a team effort. In the case of Oshii... for that scene he directly asked me to use a real music box. He told me to create a custom-made music box, because he wanted the sound to be real, authentic, nothing synthesised or digital. So the sound you hear in that scene really comes from a music box. In some scenes, if a singer appears, the scene is built giving great importance to the theme I compose or select for that particular scene.

Often, I'm tied to the script to make the setting and scene believable, although usually my involvement isn't as high as in those sequences; I don't want the music to come first and then the script.

The Teatro Cervantes in Málaga. The venue for the closing gala of the MOSMA Festival, where we met and interviewed Mr. Kawai.

Cool Japan: What is your opinion on video games as an artistic medium? How do you approach working on a video game?

Kenji Kawai: For me, there is basically no difference in the working process when composing for a video game, a movie, or a series. At least, musically, they are on the same level. You work the same way as when composing for series or cinema. Although there is one difference compared to the latter: instead of creating a complete track for a sequence, I make music samples which are then recorded in the studio.

Cool Japan: We know that, besides cinema, you have also composed music for video games, such as *Folklore* for the PlayStation 3. What differences have you noticed when working for this medium compared to the cinematic field, with which you are more associated?

Kenji Kawai: The difference is almost negligible. There are some factors to take into account, though. For example, when I create audio samples, musical tracks, I have to consider loops and repetition, so that the track can play continuously during a level or fit seamlessly with another when the player moves from one sequence to another, each with a different tone of action. I always have to find that balance. Sometimes they provide me with an image of the game for the music, but other times I don't get an image at all, and I have to innovate completely—which makes it a different experience.

Cool Japan: In the soundtrack for the *Ghost in the Shell* films, there is a clear influence of traditional Japanese music. How much do the musical heritage of your country and your birthplace —Kita-Shinagawa, where you still live— influence your work?

Kenji Kawai: Especially in *Ghost in the Shell 2: Innocence*, there was a strong connection. Elements like the taiko, the Japanese drum. In the area where I live, during local festivals —the matsuri— they use a traditional festival float. Normally, there are processions in Japan with a float, but in this area, they carry a taiko in the procession. The taiko is played as it moves, and people watch it in action during the parade. The combination of taiko and the traditional Japanese flute, the shakuhachi, occurs in these festivals. In addition, both traditional instruments mix with the sounds of the event, the festival, and the crowd. This combination creates a unique atmosphere in Shinagawa. I wanted to capture that feeling, that combination, and bring it into the animated film.

Cool Japan: As of 2016... Could you tell us what projects you are currently working on?

Kenji Kawai: Right now I have many anime series commissions. Next month [that is, August], two series for which I just composed music will be released. I've also composed for the film *Hirune Hime: Shiranai Watashi no Monogatari*.

Kenji Kawai pictured with our colleague Andrés Domenech Alcaide

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Sources

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